

Workload on Employee Performance with Burnout

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Abstract. This research is motivated by the many previous studies that examined on the workload and performance of the employees, but not mediated by burnout of employees, so the purpose of this study was to determine and analyze whether burnout mediates the effect of workload on employee performance. This study used a questionnaire which would then be distributed to the employees who work in the manufacturing company in Batam. Population of manufacturing company in Batam is 276 companies. Sampling method using slovin formula, so that the samples used were 163 manufacturing companies in Batam. The study found that burnout mediates most of the effect of work load on employee performance.

Keywords: workload, employee performance, burnout

Introduction

The success rate of a company can be seen from the company's performance in managing its resources. Companies with good performance, have good effectiveness in handling their human resources and in setting goals that must be achieved individually or organization [12]. This can be done by managing human resources well and organized in order to obtain a workforce who is satisfied with his work so as to produce maximum performance. Good employee performance is one of them can be achieved by adjusting the workload given to employees with the ability owned by employees. The division of workload is a critical early stage for an employee before work that will determine the employee's final outcome. If an employee feels overworked will cause the employee to experience a decrease in performance and result in work stress [16]. The work load is based on the utilization of available working time to perform the work, ie seen from activities, or activities performed by staff at work, whether direct, indirect, and other activities such as personal and non-productive activities [7]. Burnout is a result of prolonged stress and occurs when a person begins to question his or her personal values [8]. Research on the workload of

employee performance has been done a lot before, such as research that found that employees who have overloaded work will result in decreased employee performance [1], [11], [18], [1]. Research on burnout has also been done a lot before, such as [9] and [17] found that an employee can feel burnout when experiencing a negative perception of their work conditions, such as workload, psychological work environment. In the previous study still examined the overall working conditions, such as workload or hours of work, and no one uses employee burnout as a mediation variable.

Literature Review

Employee performance

Employee performance is the result of individual work in an organization [13]. Performance is to judge how a person has worked against a predetermined target [4]. Employee performance is the actual achievement of the employee compared to the expected performance of the employee. Expected work performance is a standard achievement that is

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arranged as a reference so that it can see the performance of employees in accordance with its position compared with the standards made. In addition it can also be seen the performance of these employees against other employees [5].

Workload

The work load is based on the utilization of available working time to perform the work, ie seen from activities, or activities performed by staff at work, whether direct, indirect, and other activities such as personal and non-productive activities [7].

Burnout on Employees

Burnout is a physical, mental, and emotional exhaustion that occurs due to stress suffered over a long period of time and involves high emotionality [15]. Burnout is a result of the stress experienced by individuals over long periods of time and with frequent intensity, characterized by physical, mental, and emotional exhaustion, and low self-esteem resulting in individuals feeling separate from their surroundings. Factors that are seen to influence the emergence of burnout, namely: [3]

1. External factors are working conditions, which include poor psychological work environment, lack of opportunities for promotion, insufficient rewards, lack of social support from superiors, job demands, monotonous work, and

2. Internal factors include age, gender, self-esteem, educational level, years of service and personality characteristics.

Previous studies [1] that examined the effect of working conditions on employee productivity on manufacturing companies in Somalia, found that there was a positive relationship between working conditions and employee performance. Similar studies [2] conducted research on employee burnout and its effect on employee performance on healthcare workers in Iran. As well as research [19] found in his research that the burden of work that is felt heavy or too much by employees will trigger employee saturation perceived that is known as job burnout syndrome.

Research Methods

The type of data used is the primary data collected through the questionnaire. The questionnaires in this

study were: Subjective Workload Assessment Technique (SWAT) [6], Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) [14] and Performance Questionnaire Design by Patterson [10]. The questionnaire was distributed to 163 manufacturing companies in Batam randomly selected with each company given 50 questionnaires. Calculation of sample using slovin formula (from 276 population, got to 163 sample).

Results and Discussion

The object of research used by researchers is the Islamic banks by using a sample of employees or staff who are still working in 2016. Based on these criteria, samples that can be used by investigators in this research were 180 respondents.

Table 1
Characteristics of Data

Description	Total
Questionnaires Distributed	200
Questionnaires were distributed	180
Questionnaire were not filled respondent	20
Questionnaire which can be sampled	180
Data outlier	0
Total sample	180

Respondents who have filled out a questionnaire study then identified based on gender. This identification of research done to determine the general characteristics of respondents.

Table 2
Characteristics of Respondents

Gender	Frequency (person)	Percentage (%)
Man	118	65.6
Woman	62	34.4
Total	180	100.0

The 180 respondents who filled out the questionnaire, it appears that the number of male respondents more than female respondents with a difference 31.2%.

Testing Instruments

Testing instrument against indicators of each variable in order to know the level of valid and reliable indicator as a measuring tool. This instrument consists of testing the validity and reliability test.

Validity test used to measure whether or not a legitimate or valid questionnaires. Researchers conducted a test by finding the correlation between scores of each item questions with a total score of each

dimension. A questionnaire considered valid if r count > r table (Ghozali, 2012).

Table 3
Validity Test

Variable	Item	Validity		Conclusion
		r count	r table	
Voice Behavior	Q1	1.000	0.1230	Valid
	Q2	0.536		Valid
Q3	0.561	Valid		
Q4	0.459	Valid		
Q5	0.433	Valid		
Q6	0.460	Valid		
Work Engagement	Q7	0.235		Valid
	Q8	0.154		Valid
	Q9	0.206		Valid
	Q10	0.125		Valid
Q11	0.200	Valid		
Q12	0.129	Valid		
Q13	0.153	Valid		
Work Motivation	Q14	0.231		Valid
	Q15	0.262		Valid
Q16	0.149	Valid		
Q17	0.253	Valid		
Employee Performance	Q18	0.150		Valid
	Q19	0.348		Valid
	Q20	0.237		Valid
	Q21	0.190		Valid

Each indicator question used by researchers to have r count larger than r table, which means that the indicator questions from each of the variables that researchers use in this study is valid to be used as a measurement variable.

Reliability is a tool to measure the reliability or reliable a questionnaire if the response to a statement consistent or stable over time. Components of the questions in the questionnaire is considered reliable and consistent with the variables in a study if it gives Cronbach alpha values. A research instruments can be declared reliable if the reliability coefficient (Cronbach alpha value) is greater than 0.60 (Ghozali, 2012).

Table 4
Reliabilities Test

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
X1_Voice Behavior	0.887	1.127
X2_Work Engagement	0.863	1.159
X3_Motivation	0.884	1.131

All variables has a Cronbach alpha value greater than the default value, 0.60. Thus, it can be concluded that all the variables that researchers use in this study is reliable.

Classic Assumption Test

Normality test purposed to test whether there is a variable in the regression model residuals have the normal distribution. This normality test can be performed on multiple linear regression test that can be seen on the histogram charts and diagrams P-P Plot. In this test, the decision-making criteria is if a curved curve in diagram form the arch histogram normal curve and also the P-P diagram shows plots Plot to follow the straight line, then the residual otherwise normal and normality assumptions are met (Hidayat, 2013).

Fig. 2. P-Plot Diagram

The arch curves at P-P diagram shows plots Plot to follow the straight line, it can be concluded that the data were normally distributed residuals and normality assumptions are met.

Table 5
Multicollinearity Test

Variable	Total Item	Reliability		Conclusion
		Alpha Cronbach	Standard	
Voice Behavior	6	0.896	0.60	Reliable
Work Engagement	7	0.893	0.60	Reliable
Work Motivation	4	0.896	0.60	Reliable
Employee Performance	4	0.893	0.60	Reliable

The data obtained from the sample there are no statistics multicollinearity because the amount of tolerance is quite high with the average value (0.878) from the value of 0.10 and VIF (variance inflation factor) to conduct voice, involvement work and work motivation (X1, X2, X3) respectively 1.127, 1.159 and 1.131 also showed none of the independent variables

that have a value of more than 10 (0.10). So we can conclude that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables. Terms to avoid multicollinearities is the tolerance value should not be less than 0.10 and VIF must not be 10 (0.10) (Ghozali, 2012).

Heteroscedasticity test aims to test the occurrence of inequality or the difference in residual variance of the observations by the observations of others. Researchers conducted the testing heteroscedasticity with glejser test by way of regressing the absolute value of the residuals of the independent variables. A good regression model in a study is not going heteroscedasticity if an independent variable has a significance value of correlation > 0.05 (Ghozali, 2012).

Table 6
Heteroscedasticity Test

Variable	Sig.	Description
Voice Behavior	0.887	No heteroscedasticity
Work Engagement	0.863	No heteroscedasticity
Work Motivation	0.884	No heteroscedasticity

All independent variables have significance value above the standard value of 0.05 indicating that all independent variables nothing significant in influencing the dependent variable, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity on data.

Hypothesis Test

The method I use to test the hypothesis in this study is a simple linear regression statistical T - test (partial). Statistical T-test was conducted to determine the effect of each independent variable partially.

Table 7
Hypothesis Test with T-Test

Model	T	Sig.
1 (Constant)	5.985	0.000
X1_Voice Behavior	1.514	0.132
X2_Work_Engagement	1.431	0.154
X3_Motivation	3.866	0.000

The results of the t test for sound behavioral variables, work engagement and motivation are 1.514, 1.431 and 3.866 with a significance value of each is 0.132, 0.154 and 0.000, so it can be concluded that H1 voice behavior, T arithmetic < T table (1,514 < 1,65346) and the significance value calculated > significance standard (0,132 > 0,05). H2 work engagement, T arithmetic < T table (1,431 < 1.65346) and the significance value calculated > significance

standard (1,154 > 0.05). H3 work motivation, T arithmetic > T table (3,886 > 1.65346) and the significance value count < significance standard.

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

Simple linear regression analysis is an analysis of the linear relationship between two or more independent variables (X) to the dependent variable (Y).

Table 8
Simple Linear Regression Testing

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	
	B	T
1 (Constant)	10.794	5.985
X1_voice behavior	0.168	1.514
X2_work engagement	0.086	1.431
X3_Motivation	0.302	3.866

The regression equation as follows:

$$Y = a + b1 * X1 + bn * Xn$$

$$IP = a + b1 * MK + b2 * PS + b3 * KK + e$$

$$IP = 10.794 + 1.514 + 1.431 * 3.866 + e$$

- IP = Individual Performance;
- WM = Work Motivation;
- VB = Voice Behavior;
- WE = Work Engagement;
- e= standard error

Constant value of (10.794), the value of positive constants show the positive influence of the independent variable (voice behavior, work engagement and motivation). When the independent variable goes up, then the individual performance variable (Y) will go up.

Regression coefficients voice behavior (X1) is 0.168 or 16.8%, it means that if the voice behavior increase unit, then individual performance (Y) will be increased by 0.168 or 16.8%. Based on calculations, it is known that the value of the coefficient T count is smaller than the value of the coefficient T table (1.514 < 1.65346), it can be concluded that the variable voice behavior (X1) has no effect on the individual performance. The regression equation $Y = 10.794 + 0.168 + e$.

Regression coefficients work engagement (X2) that is equal 0.086 (8.6%), meaning that if the variable work engagement increased unit, then individual performance variable (Y) will increase by 0.086 (8.6%). Based on the calculations, it is known that the value of the coefficient T table (1.431 < 1.65346), it

can be concluded that work engagement variables (X2) has no effect on the individual performance (Y). The regression equation $Y = 10.794 + 0.086 + e$.

Regression coefficient value variable work motivation (X3) that is equal 0.302 (30.2%), meaning that if the work motivation increased unit, then individual performance variable (Y) will increase by 0.232 (23.2%). Based on calculations, it is known that the value of the coefficient T table ($3.866 > 1.65346$), it can be concluded that work motivation has a positive influence on the individual performance (Y). The regression equation $Y = 10,794 + 0,302 + e$.

Data Analysis

Based on statistical tests that have been described, it can be concluded that the noise behavior has no effect on the performance of the individual or the hypothesis is rejected. This is because T arithmetic $<$ T table ($1.514 < 1.65346$) and the significance value calculated $>$ significance standard ($1.132 > 0.05$), while the requirement for the hypothesis is accepted if T is bigger than T table and a significance value smaller count or equal to the value of the standard significance (Raharjo, 2015). This study is not in line with previous studies conducted by Dyne (1998), Mayer (2009), Brown (2005), Hoogh (2008), Dyne (1998), Mayer (2009), Brown (2005) and Hoogh (2008).

Based on statistical tests that have been explained, it can be concluded that the involvement of labor has no effect on the performance of the individual or the hypothesis is rejected. This is because since T arithmetic $<$ T table ($1.431 < 1.65346$) and the significance value calculated $>$ significance standard ($0.154 > 0.05$). This research is not in line with research conducted by Rich (2010), Zhu (2009), and Roberson (2010).

Based on statistical tests that have been described, it can be concluded that motivation (motivation) positive effect on the performance of the individual or the hypothesis is accepted. This is because T arithmetic $>$ T table ($3.866 > 1.230$) and a significant value count $<$ significance standard ($0.000 < 0.05$). In the Islamic banks, one important aspect in the management of the company to maintain and improve morale in order to increase the productivity or performance of employees is to provide motivation for them. This study are consistent with previous studies conducted by Robbins (2012), Maulani (2003), and Darmanwansyah (2012). One important aspect in the management of the company to maintain and improve

morale in order to increase the productivity or performance of employees is to provide motivation for them.

Conclusion

This study has a model to test the effect of sound behavior, work engagement and motivation on the performance of individual Islamic bank in the city of Batam. Based on these test results, it can be concluded that Voice behavior does not have a significant effect on the individual performance. Work engagement had no effect on the performance of the individual (employee). Job involvement here means the bank management does not necessarily involve its employees in every activity of the company, only certain employees are involved. Work motivation positive influence on employee performance. With high morale (high motivation), the employee may issue its ability as much as possible in order to realize the goals together.

Implication

This study examined the effect of sound behavior, work engagement and work motivation on employee performance. From this study it can be concluded that the performance of the individual (employee) can increase if the work motivation can be fulfilled to the employee. The results could be useful for managers of human resources (HR) banking and non-banking company as a reference in maintaining the performance of individual employees to the company's survival. Individual performance can maximize employee productivity that can support the survival and ideals of the company.

Limitation

Based on the above conclusions, while the natural limitations that researchers. Companies that used in this study is limited to the banking sector, especially in the Islamic bank. There are several questionnaires that were rejected by one of the banks studied sariah. There are some Islamic bank employees or staff who may fill out a questionnaire does not fit the circumstances, so there is some inaccurate data. During the study, researchers found there were several employees or staff who are doing office tasks that must be resolved, so that was not optimal in answering questions. Complicating the proposed permit

researchers to the Islamic bank which is the object of research. This is because the parties wish the researchers made the object of research is not their memorandum of understanding (MoU) with the campus.

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